

Environmental Justice through Open Source Cloud Native Tools: A Racial Legacy Still Visible from Space

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Summary

1968: In the same year as NASA's first manned mission to the moon, racially segregated housing became illegal with the Fair Housing Act. The law would now ban practices known as **redlining** – in which the federal government's Home Owners Loan Corporation dividing cities into areas graded 'minimal risk' to 'hazardous' for home loans based largely on racial and ethnic make-up (Nelson et al 2022). But the consequences of such practices are not easily reversed. More than 50 years later, scientists can still see the pattern of the inequalities etched onto those maps even from space (Schell et al, 2020). This educational module will seek to introduce students to the open source platforms and tools used to manipulate and analyze NASA's open earth observation imagery through the lens of examining the environmental legacy of redlining practices in major urban areas. We will introduce key concepts of cloud-native geospatial workflows including STAC, COG, and GDAL Virtual Filesystem to allow students to leverage analysis against terrabytes of NASA data. The module design is also deeply rooted in pedagogical practices established by education research literature to increase engagement and reach an inclusive audience (Handelsman et al. 2004; Allen & Tanner 2005). The module will be provided in both R and Python and be made available in both English and Spanish translations.

Background: The Science on Impacts of Redlining

The government lending practices now known as **redlining** were created at the height of the Great Depression in the 1930s (ex in Fig 1). Extensive research has demonstrated both the discriminatory nature of these “risk assessments” on the basis of ethnicity and nationality (e.g. Jackson, 1980, Light 2010) and the myriad social (e.g. Wilder, 2001) and environmental consequences associated with these patterns. Redlined urban areas remain associated with higher temperatures, worse air quality, lower biodiversity, and – as we shall focus on here – fewer trees and parks (Schell 2020). These issues have also been highlighted in widespread media coverage including the NY Times (Plumer et al, 2020) and Washington

Fig 1. 1937 map of San Francisco showing Home Owners Loan Corp (HOLC) grades redlining primarily immigrant and black neighborhoods as 'high risk'

Post (Fears 2022). This module uses this scientifically and societally important issue which many students may have encountered through both such media coverage and their own lived experiences as the motivating foundation through which to explore the hard evidence behind these stark conclusions first hand. To do so, students will learn to manipulate NASA satellite imagery from the LANDSAT missions and among other observation platforms which can be used to assess urban greenness today and in the recent past, against this racist legacy. Decades of educational research have emphasized the importance of teaching new skills in an *authentic context* and engages *prior knowledge* (e.g. Anderson 1996; Greeno 2006), which is especially critical to the goal of broadening participation in data science. A Prior pilot of a draft of this module by the PI in university classrooms has helped both refine the approach and demonstrate this effectiveness, as has been assessed in evaluations from peers, professional education observers, and student participants.

Accessing & Analyzing Cloud-based NASA Data

This module will emphasize the access NASA satellite imagery datasets and adoption of cloud-native, **open-source** approaches for its analysis. Despite the entrenchment of many proprietary products and platforms for geospatial analysis, especially within the earth and environmental sciences communities, open source and cloud native tools are now rapidly democratizing access and enabling new and potentially transformative applications.

In this module, students will be introduced to NASA's long running LANDSAT earth observation platform. Students will learn to search the Spatial-Temporal Assets Catalogues (STAC) to identify satellite imagery data covering major US cities. Students will be introduced to fundamentals of geospatial analysis such as coordinate reference systems, the simple features standard for defining polygons and raster formats common in remote earth observation data. Students will construct custom metadata filters to identify assets with low cloud cover. Then without downloading these large assets, students will leverage the GDAL Virtual Filesystem Interface and Virtual Tiles to execute geospatial analysis tasks including:

- extracting coordinate reference systems,
- re-projecting data into alternative reference systems,

Mean NDVI of San Fransisco during summer 2022, computed from Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF satellite imagery using cloud-native toolset (GDAL virtual tiles & virtual filesystem in R & Python)

- cropping satellite imagery to desired focal polygon corresponding the city of interest,
- computing custom function calculations across multiple bands (e.g. calculating NDVI from red and near-infrared bands)
- constructing virtual mosaics (GDAL VRT) spanning multiple satellite images
- extracting mean pixel values for each polygon
- generating visualizations comparing greenness of each region relative to its redlining status (HOLC Grade)
- Authoring their own reproducible notebooks in either R or Python documenting their analysis and conclusions

Open-source software, standards, and visualization tools

In contrast to methods and tools typically taught and employed in earth and environmental science courses and research, this module emphasizes **three core open science** advances in this space: (1) **open metadata**: Spatial-Temporal Assets Catalog (STAC) Specification, an open source standard for describing metadata of spatial-temporal data products including many open data products of NASA, (2) **Open data formats** in the form of Cloud-Optimized GeoTIFF, a spatio-temporal data structure optimized to maximize performance of “cloud native” workflows which rely on range-request based access over a network connection in place of the classical, POSIX-based methods which assume data sources is always accessed from local disks, and (3) **Open source software** Numerous innovations introduced into software libraries of the Open Source Geospatial Foundation (OSGeo, which maintains GDAL, PROJ and GEOS open source projects) and the Pangeo community which both implement interoperable open source tools that take advantage of these cloud-native range-requests (specifically, the GDAL protocols for virtual filesystem Interfaces, VSI, and Virtual Tiles, VRT). Collectively, these three elements allow students to construct and compute their own “data cubes” on demand without relying on proprietary platforms such as Google Earth Engine or precomputed assets (Appel & Pebesma, 2019). An example of this process as expressed in open source R code is shown in Box 1.

```

1 library(rstac)
2 library(gdalcubes)
3
4 ## STAC search for SF in summer
5 items <- stac("https://planetarycomputer.microsoft.com/api/stac/v1") |>
6   stac_search(collections = "landsat-c2-l2",
7             bbox = c(-122.51006, 37.70801, -122.36268, 37.80668),
8             datetime = "2022-06-01/2022-08-31") |>
9   get_request() |>
10  items_sign(sign_fn = sign_planetary_computer())
11
12 ## Metadata filter
13 col <- stac_image_collection(items$features,
14                             asset_names = c("red", "nir08"),
15                             property_filter = \(x) {x[["eo:cloud_cover"]] < 5})
16
17 ## Define desired resolution of the space-time data cube
18 cube <- cube_view(srs = "EPSG:4326",
19                  extent = list(t0 = "2022-06-01", t1 = "2022-08-01",
20                               left = box[1], right = box[3],
21                               top = box[4], bottom = box[2]),
22                  nx = 2400, ny = 2400, dt = "P1M",
23                  aggregation = "median", resampling = "average")
24
25 # Cloud-native lazy evaluation via GDAL virtual systems
26 ndvi <- raster_cube(col, cube) |>
27   select_bands(c("red", "nir08")) |>
28   apply_pixel("(nir08-red)/(nir08+red)", "NDVI") |>
29   reduce_time(c("mean(NDVI)"))
30 # Visualization
31 plot(ndvi, col = viridisLite::viridis, zlim=c(-0.2,1))

```

Box 1: Example of on-demand data cube creation using STAC and GDAL to compute NDVI from NASA Level 2 Landsat Collection in R. Virtual tile construction, aggregation and downscaling resampling (via `gdalwarp`) achieve a data cube at the desired resolution. This is a scalable workflow that can run with minimal resource requirements (less than 1 GB RAM and without local storage) due to the network-based protocol.

Combining spatial metadata from STAC and cloud-native (that is, network-based range request protocols) access from software (GDAL VSI) and data structures (COG) means that data cubes can be calculated efficiently from data hosted on cloud-based object stores (including Amazon Web Services, Azure, and open source platforms such as CEPH and MINIO) with only client-side tools and minimal footprint in computer memory (RAM) or disk storage. This democratizes access by making open source geospatial analysis possible in virtual environments such as UC Berkeley's DataHub (an open-source JupyterHub-based platform used at Berkeley and other institutions which supports computational based instruction for tens of thousands for students) or GitHub's Codespaces (which now has a free educational tier). Because this workflow relies on widely recognized open data, open standards, and low-level open libraries of OSGEO, it is possible to teach and use these concepts in both the R and python environments with little alteration to core concepts. Students who complete the module using one software environment (e.g. R) will find very similar code and analogous workflows such as STAC, virtual tiles, etc in the python version.

This open standard also means that students can easily adapt the methods they learn to query the huge array of other data products from NASA and others that can also be discovered in STAC catalogs, from MODIS earth observation data, to NOAA GEFS 30-day weather forecasts to eBird status and trends models of bird species around the world. This module emphasizes access to data from cloud-based object stores such as Microsoft Planetary Computer and the Amazon Web Services (AWS)-hosted Element84 catalogs of open NASA data, enabling high-performance scalable analysis. This stands in contrast to established approaches around proprietary software and platforms such as Google Earth Engine, and ESRI products, while providing performance and scalability of cloud-native approaches and the extensibility of open source. This approach can also be contrasted with alternative open methods which were more siloed by product, each with its own formats and interfaces (e.g. accessing MODIS data directly through ORNL DAAC), rather than leveraging an interoperable open standard like STAC.

Creation, management, and sharing of reproducible workflows

In this module, students will learn about the creation, management, and sharing of reproducible workflows. The module will be made open and freely available on GitHub as a repository template under permissive open source licenses (MIT for code, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 copyright for educational content). Students can access the module through open source version control software, git, or directly using the open source platform GitLab or commercial platform GitHub. Students will create their own GitHub repositories from the template repository, push their content to the notebook, and manage public or private access. Module content will be formulated using the executable notebook formats in Quarto for the R version and Jupyter for the Python version (Note that both formats support both languages and software can automatically translate between quarto and ipynb format).

An open, extensible contribution module

This module will be carefully designed to maximize open, extensible design that allows other instructors to not only reuse but also adapt the material to additional datasets and questions with minimal effort. These design elements will include:

- All module material will be freely available on GitHub with a permanent archive of each release under versioned DOIs preserved on the Zenodo scientific data repository.
- All software and analysis techniques have been selected to minimize barriers to entry in contributions and extensions. For instance, providing both R and Python

versions of the module allows better engagement from both communities. Meanwhile, emphasis on cross-environment open standards and tools like STAC and GDAL that work very similarly across both languages maximize the ability to leverage contributions from either one back into the other. These standards-based tools also facilitate extension by minimizing the friction required to adapt the module to other datasets. For instance, very little code must be changed to adapt the example based on Landsat level 2 data to address the analysis MODIS products instead – as both are available in COG formats in a STAC catalog such as Planetary Computer. This stands in contrast to most tutorials users will find on an internet search that discuss more siloed and less cloud-native methods for downloading these different products.

- An open container standard (docker)-based environment following best practice development tools will allow users to quickly drop into an interactive environment to explore and test potential contributions. This environment can also be run through continuous integration systems such as GitHub Actions to provide automated quality checks on community contributions to the module.
- Module tasks are carefully scoped to run across a wide variety of platforms, and especially to be able to take advantage of free-tier cloud compute systems such as GitHub Codespaces. A custom devcontainer setup allows users to launch into a VM with the necessary specialized open source software pre-installed, and provides access to high-bandwidth network operations crucial for cloud-based workflows. At the same time, these free-tier platforms tightly limit available resources in RAM and compute. A module design that emphasizes big-data practices of out-of-core operations in cloud-native workflows allows users to leverage these very large datasets even in RAM-limited environments.

Building collaboratively from existing content

This module is built around allowing students to reproduce existing scientific studies in environmental justice, remote sensing, and environment using open NASA data and open source software. The focus on existing research will highlight the contributions of BIPOC scholars which have historically been under-represented in classroom examples.

Multiple language versions of content

This module will be made available in both **English** and **Spanish**. The intended graduate student researcher supporting this project is a native Spanish speaker, and the PI is familiar with providing multilingual support as pioneered in the rOpenSci project, which has several years experience in providing multilingual software code review and community blog to bridge language barriers (Boettiger et al 2015).

Narrative and executable content

The module will be provided using interactive notebook formats. Specifically, the Python version will be provided as Jupyter Notebooks (in English & Spanish), and the R version will be provided as a Quarto Notebook (in English & Spanish). An executable devcontainer environment [devcontainer] will allow students to deploy the notebook from any browser into a free, interactive GitHub Codespaces environment, or clone the notebook to local or other cloud-based environments using open source tools such as Git, RStudio, & Jupyter.

Summary Table of Work Effort

Work Efforts to be funded by this proposal					
Name	Role	Commitment (FTE)			
		Y1	Y2		Total
Graduate Student	GSR	5 mo	5 mo		10 mo
Total funded work effort		5 mo	5 mo		10 mo
Work Efforts proposed, but NOT to be funded by this proposal					
Name	Role	Commitment (FTE)			
		Y1	Y2		Total
PI	PI	1 mo	1 mo		2 mo
Total unfunded work effort		1 mo	1 mo		2 mo
TOTAL Work Efforts proposed (Funded + Unfunded)					
Name	Role	Commitment (FTE)			
		Y1	Y2		Total
PI	PI	1 mo	1 mo		2 mo
Graduate Student	GSR	5 mo	5 mo		10 mo
Grand Total of work effort		6 mo	6 mo		12 mo

REDACTED BUDGET				
	From:	6/1/2023	6/1/2024	
	To:	5/31/2024	5/31/2025	
BUDGET CATEGORY		Period 1	Period 2	Total
SALARY		x	x	x
BENEFITS		x	x	x
TRAVEL		0	0	0
MATERIALS & SUPPLIES		0	0	0
EQUIPMENT		0	0	0
CONSULTANT		0	0	0
SUBRECIPIENT		0	0	0
TOTAL DIRECT COSTS		-	-	-
Indirect (F&A) Costs				
	<i>F&A Base: MTDC</i>	-	-	-
Indirect (F&A) Costs	xx	x	x	x
TOTAL ESTIMATED COSTS PER YEAR		x	x	
TOTAL ESTIMATED COSTS FOR PROPOSED PROJECT PERIOD				x

REDACTED BUDGET JUSTIFICATION

PERSONNEL

Graduate Student Researcher: The GSR will assist the PI, as directed, in conducting research and contribute to the drafting and dissemination of results. They will commit X months.

FRINGE BENEFITS:

Composite Benefit Rates (CBR) have been reviewed and federally approved by the Department of Health and Human Services (DHHS) for use by all fund sources. Fringe benefits are assessed as a percentage of the respective employee's salary.

Full remission of tuition, fees, and graduate student health insurance is provided to all graduate students who are employed on-campus 45% time or greater during the academic year.

INDIRECT COSTS:

Indirect costs are based on negotiated rates with the cognizant federal authority and are applied at a rate of x%. Indirect costs are applied using the Modified Total Direct Cost (MTDC) formula. Modified total direct costs exclude equipment, capital expenditures, charges for patient care, student tuition remission, rental costs of off-site facilities, scholarships, and fellowships, participant support costs and the portion of each subgrant and subcontract in excess of \$25,000.

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Open-Source Science Development Plan

All curriculum products will be permissively licensed (MIT licensed software, CC-BY licensed content) and contributed to the TOPS GitHub. Archival copies will be imported into the Zenodo Scientific Data Repository automatically when new releases are tagged in GitHub using the Zenodo-GitHub integration webhook. Zenodo will assign each new release with a sequential, linked digital object identifier (DOI) and parse appropriate DataCITE metadata to facilitate FAIR [@fair] access.

The GitHub repository will be organized according to best practices (as exhibited in the rOpenSci and JOSS software peer review communities, see) to facilitate contribution, including:

- A clearly stated open source LICENSE.md file (MIT license)
- A CONTRIBUTING.md document outlining the process for contributions, including updates or extensions to the educational module software or documentation
- A CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md file outlining appropriate, based on the Contributor Covenant v2.1 [@covenant <https://www.contributor-covenant.org>]
- A detailed README.md describing the purpose of the educational module, where to get started as an instructor, student, or contributor, and an overview of the module contents. Badge icons at the top of the README will provide quickstart links to begin the interactive module in Jupyter (python) or quarto (R) notebooks and the results of the reproducibility and linting checks run by the continuous integration system.
- A continuous integration system will provide: (a) automated quality control checks to ensure that the code used in the module is actively working, (b) linting checks to ensure that all code, including community contributions, conforms to established best practices in code formatting and style, (c) automatic deployment of a static website in gh-pages, providing up-to-date and user-friendly documentation of the module design and objectives.

All of the module development will work in a collaborative and open fashion. The PI has an established track record of open source development of educational modules and infrastructure. Module development builds on the PI's previous experience in developing and teaching modules which have been developed in the open on GitHub through the course, "ESPM-157: Data Science for Global Change Ecology" which has been taught to students at UC Berkeley (<https://github.com/espm-157/spatial-template>).